

Statistical View of Quantum Mechanics with Time Included

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In a previous note (1), we tried to present a statistical view of quantum mechanics for a bound state. Time was ignored and it was suggested that at a point x , $V(x)$ and kinetic energy are both averages which add to a constant E . It was also suggested that $V(x) = \sum_k V_k f(k,x)$ and $KE(x) = [\sum_p p^2/2m f(p,x) a(p)] / W(x)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) f(p,x)$. We tried to argue that by using conservation of momentum and introducing statistical uncertainty in x , one may obtain $f(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$. In other words, if a particle is in a momentum state p_1 at x at an instant in time t_1 , it may be in p_2 at t_2 , due to the action of the potential. Thus, to measure energy takes a certain interval of time. This seems to suggest an uncertainty in measuring energy and time together. Furthermore, the interaction of $f(p,x)$ with $V_k f(k,x)$ leads to the particle jumping from one state to another, so as energy is being measured, the state represented by the normalization constant $W(x)$ may be evolving i.e. $W(x,t)$. In this note, we try to consider aspects of time in this statistical picture, which are present even in the bound state case, as has been noted in previous notes, which started with $\exp(ipx)$. In this note, we try to argue that quantum mechanics seems to follow directly from statistical arguments, without the need for $\exp(ipx)$ or operators as a starting point.

Classical Mechanics versus Quantum Mechanics

In classical mechanics, one knows the momentum and energy of a particle at each x and t . For a bound state, a particle may have p to the right at x at t_1 and p to the left at x at t_2 , thus there is a periodicity with these two distinct time points. In a quantum mechanical bound state, one has only one particle, but it may be in different momentum states at the same x at different times. This includes both the forward and backwards momentum of the classical case. For example, consider the wavefunction for a particle in a box: $C \sin(px)$. Here p is an average momentum, but both a forward average $\exp(ipx)$ and a backwards one $\exp(-ipx)$ are included. Thus, the quantum mechanical average is already curious as it considers all possible momenta at a point x . Treating quantum mechanics as a statistical theory and assuming a particle may have many different p values at the same x seems to suggest these must occur at different times. Yet, one must measure all of these p values to calculate the energy, as one is taking statistical average. As a consequence, it seems it takes a ΔT (time) to measure the energy, even for a bound state. Thus, there is uncertainty in energy and time because one needs to consider time in intervals of ΔT . It is also possible a state is evolving in time, but this seems to occur through interactions with a potential. Thus, the measurement of average energy and the evolution of the system both seem to occur within ΔT and are not separable.

Meaning of Time in a Quantum Bound State

In (1), time did not appear in the formulation of bound state quantum mechanics. Rather, one considered an average over p values i.e.

$$\left[\sum_{\text{over } p} p^2/2m a(p) \exp(ipx) \right] / \left[\sum_{\text{over } p} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right] + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

Where the wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_{\text{over } p} a(p) \exp(ipx)$ ((2)). At first, $\exp(ipx)$ was replaced by $f(p,x)$ and it was argued that $\exp(ipx)$ follows from conservation of momentum and statistical uncertainty of x for $f(p,x)$. No time variable appears explicitly, yet time is present because each p occurs at a different time t . Furthermore, for a quantum bound particle, just as for a classical one, a particle may be moving in one direction at time t_1 and in the opposite direction at time t_2 . Thus, there is a frequency for both cases that should be explicitly contained in ((1)).

Thus, it takes a certain amount of time ΔT related to a frequency to measure E average at x . For a bound state, one argues that E average is the same for all x . Matters become more complicated if one considers $W(x,t)$. What does t mean in such a case when $W(x)$ already incorporates time and is statistical? For $W(x)$ (for a bound state), the time interval needed to measure E is ΔT , because the system repeats itself in a sense each ΔT interval. For an evolving system, however, it takes ΔT for an energy measurement to occur, but the system is evolving at the same time, so $W(x,t)$ seems to make sense. Even for a bound state, the order of occurrence of p states changes during each cycle, so it seems that there is a kind of time evolution occurring. For example, ((1)) may be rewritten for each $\exp(ipx)$ as:

$$p^2/2m a(p) + \sum_{\text{over } k} V(k) a(p-k) = E a(p) \quad \text{where } p \text{ and } k \text{ are vectors} \quad ((3))$$

Thus, various $\exp(ipx)$ are colliding with different $\exp(ikx)$ and one has a dynamic system. Even if the magnitude of $W(x)$ is not changing, there is cycling motion occurring in time. Thus, for a bound state one may postulate a $W(x,t)$ such that dW/dt ($d/dt = \text{partial derivative}$) is not 0. The magnitude of $W(x,t)$, however should change in time, thus one does not want a real time portion. Given ((1)) and the idea of dW/dt , it seems one may write:

$$H W(x,t) = i \frac{d}{dt} W = E W(x) \exp(-iEt) \quad \text{for a bound state } \hbar=1 \quad ((4))$$

Even though an energy measurement takes ΔT , one may use any value of time in $\exp(-iEt)$, but the system repeats itself each ΔT . Thus, the cyclical nature of $\exp(-iEt)$ seems to make sense and it adds nothing to the magnitude of $W(x)$. Just as in the case of $\exp(ipx)$, trying to remove time from the bound state statistical picture, introduces it as a complex function of modulus 1. In this case, the periodicity is strongly linked to physical arguments, i.e. the time cycling in a bound state which exists even for classical physics. For $\exp(ipx)$, one needs to introduce the idea of a wavelength, an idea which does not appear in classical physics (in usual circumstances)

Time Dependent Case

For a non-bound state, one may still measure $E(t)$, but it takes a time ΔT in which to do this because of the statistical nature of the occurrences of different p states. At the same, the interaction of the particle with $V(x)$ occurring during the measurement of E evolves the system. Thus, ((4)) is still a candidate for the time dependent non-bound case. For the bound state, it was seen that the statistical picture includes particles moving forwards and backwards, so when solving the time dependent case, one should be careful of this as well.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum mechanics is a type of statistical theory which allows for multiple momentum values at different times at the same point x . These are stirred up by interactions with the potential which may be written as $\sum_k V_k f(k,x)$. The average kinetic energy at x is given by: $[\sum_p p^2/2m a(p) f(p,x,t)] / W(x,t)$ where the wavefunction (or normalization constant is given by: $\sum_p f(p,x,t)$. For a bound state, one tries to remove space x from the picture for $f(p,x,t)$. "X" must remain as an important factor for the average kinetic or potential energy at a point. Even though one tries to remove time, there is cycling occurring because each p is converted into another due to $V(x)$. Thus, $W(x,t)$ is really time dependent, even though it takes a time ΔT to establish a measurement of E . During this time, the system may be evolving, thus the calculation of energy and the change of the statistical system in time are intimately linked. We argue that even for the bound state $W(x,t)$, the t portion cannot increase or decrease W in real space. It should also be periodical, because there is periodicity in a bound system, both classical and quantum. Thus, $\exp(iEt)$ emerges as a solution of: $H W(x,t) = i d/dt W(x,t)$ where d/dt means partial derivative. This is interesting because the changing wavefunction incorporates "energy". For the bound state, this change in time is due to a cycling resonance which is linked directly to a specific energy.

In the statistical approach described above, we have tried to avoid using operators or the idea of a wavefunction. $W(x,t)$ is a normalization in the statistical approach. We try to argue that quantum mechanics may be formulated as a statistical theory (in which one tries to introduce as much uncertainty as possible, e.g. x for $f(p,x)$ and time in general. From this, it follows that one has $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ as solutions which then leads to physical descriptions for the bound state. $dW(x,t)/dt$ and the idea of measuring energy in a ΔT time also carry over to the non-bound state case.

References

Ruggeri, Francesco R. Position Uncertainty in a Statistical View of Quantum Bound States (preprint, zenodo, 2020)